

Co-creating solutions with students: Development of an anonymous problem-reporting system

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Problem

At the Mulford Health Science Library, if a student had concerns about other students' behaviors (most often talking too loudly), they would walk down the main staircase to the circulation desk.

After making the report, the student would walk back up the staircase, followed by a staff member, who would ask the students in question to change their behavior.

It was clear to everyone which student reported the issue, which led to animosity between the reporting student and the reported students.

Main study space on the fifth floor of the Mulford Library. It is one large room, so it is easy for people to see who is walking down the staircase to the circ desk to report concerns.

Objective

Student representatives on the Mulford Library Advisory Committee asked for an anonymous way to report concerns in the library.

Project Constraints

There were several constraints for this project:

- Students requested that they be allowed to report concerns anonymously.
- Reports needed to be pushed to staff members so they could see reports in real-time.
- Ideally, the solution would use a system that staff members did not have to learn.
- Solution was free for the library to use (existing University software or free software).

Options

Some solutions were considered and discarded:

- Allowing students to text library staff; judged to be too complex, costly, and potentially not anonymous.
- Creating a new queue on the University's IM reference platform (LibraryH3lp); required staff to learn a new platform.
- Creating a form; report information would be emailed to on-duty staff; nearly judged to be too complex because how would the form know who was working at a given time?

After discussion with staff, we chose a variation on the third option: using a form to collect reports, which would then be sent to a new departmental email, which would then forward the reports to all staff, regardless of who was working.

Staff found this solution acceptable because they did not have to learn a new platform, they have their email open all the time while they are at work, and it was easy for them to delete reports that came in while they were not on duty.

In addition, this solution relied upon software that was already available at the University: QuestionPro and Outlook. TellMulford was born.

Form Structure

Students can access TellMulford via a QR code posted at each study desk and each study room. It is NOT available online because we want reports from within the library, not elsewhere.

First question is the type of concern: noise, facility issue, safety concern, and other. This initiates survey logic, so that the next page of questions is relevant to the concern.

The next page asks for information about the issue (questions vary based on type of concern): more about the concern and location of concern. This page also provides information to the reporting student, such as how the library can't control the noise of rain on the skylight or noise from events on the library plaza.

Finally, there is an option for the student to leave their name and email if they would like us to follow up with them.

Response

Students have been using TellMulford to anonymously or confidentially report concerns to library staff.

The most reported concerns are those dealing with noise, which is consistent with reports before the form was implemented.

Most students provide enough detail for staff to easily identify those whose behavior instigated the report: location on the fifth floor, number of students in the group, and sometimes specifics of what the students are wearing.

Thankfully, we have received few safety or facility-related reports thus far.

Staff report satisfaction with TellMulford, as it is easy for them to identify the issue in the library and to address it. Deleting reports that come in before shifts has not been a barrier.

Conclusion

TellMulford has proven to be a successful solution to a student request for anonymous reporting. This solution satisfies all project constraints. It is easy for students to make reports and easy for staff to receive and deal with reports. It uses software that is available at the university, incurring no cost to the library.